

Humanoid Robot as Assistant Tutor for Autistic Children

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to propose an interactive tutoring environment, using humanoid robots, to support children with autism disorders. Statistics indicate an increase in the use of robotics (more than 5000 robots) in more than 50 countries for teaching and learning purposes. Therefore, the process of choosing the modern teaching method that appropriates to the level of the student is a crucial matter. The proposed interactive teaching framework consists of three phases, including preparing the suitable class materials, programming the NAO robot, and evaluating the performance of the teaching methods on students' communication and academic skills. Besides, it implements a multiple-scenario approach to developing lesson plans and verifying student acknowledgments to lessons and updating the curriculum as necessary. The robot is used as an assistant tool to help students read stories, spell words, and correct students' answers to a particular Math question. The results show that the use of robots as tutors help students learn difficult topics with their native language easily and enjoy educational gaming activities. It also helped teachers to create new lessons by browsing online teaching resources and adding them to the lesson plan based on the course profile schedule and students' feedback. Also, the participants indicated that using a tutor robot is offering no bias against students' gender, race, socioeconomic status, personal preference, or other considerations.

Keywords:

Robot Tutor, NAO robot, Teaching Methods, children with Autism.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to recent developments in artificial intelligence and robotic technology, robotics has become one of the most promising fields in the current decade [1]. The use of robots to assist teaching and learning on different levels has become an extensive research field. Also, the latest statistics show the total sales of professional service robots in 2017 increased by 85% (to 109,543 units) compared with 59,269 units in 2016. This is an increase of 39%, reaching 6.6 billion US dollars [2] as shown in Figure 1.

Many research papers explored and reviewed the implementation of robots for many fields, including healthcare [3-5], industrial [6-7], and education [8-12]. Chang [8] explored the previous studies regarding the use of educational robots and analyzed the features of robots and instructional media. Alemi M. et al. [9] examined the impact of utilizing a humanoid robot as

a tutor in teaching a foreign language for children. The research shows that there was an increase in students' performance. Fernández-Llamas et al. [10] investigated the impact of employing a social robot as a teacher in teaching and compared it to a human teacher. The research explains that there is no significant difference in performance between the two teaching methods. Jabar et al., [11] developed a questionnaire to determine the satisfaction rate of using a humanoid robot in teaching and learning. The result shows that 71% of the participants agreed and believed in using humanoid robots in teaching and learning. Cheng, Y.W et al. [12] deployed a literature review for determining the fundamental applications of educational robots. The results have proven that robotics, linguistics, social, and education are the top applications. Also, the use of robotics in teaching Pre-and primary schools was the most likely to adopt educational robots in the future.

Figure 1: Sales value of service robots in the World

The robot has many useful properties that enable it to contribute to raising the educational efficiency of students and make it a valuable tool for learning. The robot can flexibly and efficiently perform repetitive tasks and provide a platform for the presentation of digital data and lessons. The type and shape of the robot help to increase the students' likeliness to engage with the learning material and improve communication skills. The robot provides an interactive and attractive environment that helps

motivate students to learn. The robot also supports the development of learning skills, communication, and collaboration between students to perform assignments and joint projects [13]. Use of robots in education is a promising research field because of many factors that need to be addressed and investigated. Therefore, this paper aims to suggest a teaching framework based on robots as a potential tutor to assist in teaching Autistic children at different levels.

2.SOCIAL ROBOTS & AUTISTIC CHILDREN

Social robots can communicate and act with people by simulating human social behaviors such as speech, hearing, sight, movement, and response to commands dynamically and vocally. A humanoid robot is a type of social robot with different shape and size that interface and interacts with people on a day to day basis and could play an essential role in human society in the future. Human-robot interaction (HRI) specifies a communication relationship between human and humanoid robots. The new development in HRI has extended its functions to assist the children suffering from Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASD). These functions incorporate many areas like socialization, communication, and social behavior through robot-based mediation [14]. According to new records of the "World Health Organization", almost 1 in 160 children are classified with ASD symptoms [15]. The previous research clarified that HRI is a particular focus for teaching and training children with ASD.

3.LITERATURE SURVEY

Many researchers discussed and proposed solutions for teaching and educating children with Autism based on different methods. Spolaôr, N. et al. [16] implemented a mobile robot based on an experimental study. The results show that half of the participants indicated that the robot improves autistic children's social skills. Dautenhahn, K et al. [17] used a Humanoid robot called "Doll" based on conversation analysis (CA) in England. The findings of this research show that the use of "Doll" enhances the attention of Autistic children. Robins, B. et al. [18] implemented different robot toys as Assistive Technology (AT) to increase or improve the capabilities of children with special needs. The results show that children like to interact more with a plain and featureless robot over human-robot.

Kozima, H. et al. [20] develop an experimental study using the human arm and a robot arm to help children do their assessments. Assistive Technology (AT) is aimed to examine the possibility of implementing the robots in the learning process. The results show that the robot helps children to move and act faster. De Silva et al. [24] used social assistive robotics therapy systems to help children with Autism Spectrum Disorder. The experimental study was implemented in Australia and the results show that the robot was socially assistive in a therapeutic setting for children with ASD. Feil-Seifer, D. et al. [31] used the NAO robot as an experimental study in Malaysia. The study proposed guidelines,

rules and procedures to serve as therapy for children with Autism. Dickstein-Fischer et al. [34] deploy an experimental study based on the KASPAR robot in UAS. The results show that the robot helps children with Autism to increase body awareness, self-sense, and collaborative play. Jeff Goodman [38] reviewed and analyzed the use of different social and humanoid robots such as NAO, KASPAR, Robota, and Probo to teach autistic children. The results indicate that the robots enhance the social interactions and communication skills of ASD children. There is a need for implementing and deploying new information technologies and tools to enhance the teaching and learning methods [40]. Table 1 presents the full review of the literature of different approaches to teaching children with Autism based robot.

4.RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, we designed and developed an experimental framework based on NAO robots for teaching and educating children. A quantitative and qualitative research methods were utilized to achieve the objectives of this research and to solve the issues identified in the review of literature based on the critical analysis of previous studies. The data collation gathering base on a personal interview. The proposed framework implements a multiple-scenario approach to developing lesson plans. This is in addition to monitoring and verifying student acknowledgments to lessons and updating the curriculum as necessary, as shown in Figure 2.

5.PROPOSED FRAMEWORK DEMONSTRATION

This paper is comprised of both theoretical and practical parts of using the robot in teaching and educating. It proposed an interactive teaching framework based on the interaction between the three system actors (Tutor, Robot, and Student), as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Actors interaction in the proposed teaching framework

The tutor implements several teaching lessons on the NAO robot, and the student can hear and interact with robots using voice, touch, and movement. Then, the robot interprets the student inquiry and acts accordingly, as shown in Figure 4. In this

lesson, the student interactively asks the NAO robot a math question, and the robot will use the speech recognition to interpret the meaning of the question, and then give the correct answer if it is multiplication or division process.

In another lesson, the NAO robot tells a story with full emotional movement, and the students listen and learn as shown in Figure 5. Then the student can act with the robot by voice or tactile touch. These buttons have an output that will allow trigger procedure to run once the robot detects and reacts to the student’s touch.

Figure 4. A Math lesson sample of the proposed teaching framework

The curriculum update is done based on the feedback that the tutor gets from the students. Besides, there are several practice tests that were designed to assess student performance and knowledge [41]. The results of the experiment will be used as a backward feeding data to update the curriculum and improve the lessons.

Figure 5. A Story lesson sample of the proposed teaching framework

6. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK DEMONSTRATION

This paper aims to discuss the importance of robotics in education and its impact on the students' social and educational skills. Educational robotics provide ideal platforms for all students to be introduced to topics related to science, technology, engineering, mathematics, physics, and programming. The literature review of existing research studies and the results of practical tests clearly show that robot based teaching improves children's communication skills and ability to read stories.

Robots also enhance problem-solving techniques and promote active learning, which can be adapted to existing school programs and quickly enhance and update the class materials. More work still needs to be done to determine the proper teaching methods and materials. The relationship between the direct (teaching and assessment method) and indirect factors (socio-economic, financial support) that affect the students' performance also needs to be addressed. Another direction for future work is to apply low price robots for low-income countries.

However, a valid questionnaire should be designed and developed to answer the research questions such as:

- How impactful is the implementation of artificial robots in education?
- How does teaching based on artificial robots correlate with student performance?
- How does teaching based on artificial robots correlate with student engagement?

The future work is to add more teaching lessons and to use flipped classes to increase the student-centered methods. More interactive lessons that ensure to engage the student in discussion topics between the robot and the student should also be designed.

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Table 1 survey of research papers on the using robot method

Ref. No/ Year	Robot Name	Method	Location	Results
[16] / 2004	Mobile robots	Experimental Study based robotic and software.	Switzerland	Half of the participants indicate that the robot improves the social skills of Autistic children.
[17] /2004	Humanoid robot doll	Conversation Analysis (CA)	England	The using of robot doll enhance the attention of the Autistic children.
[18] /2006	different robot toys	Assistive Technology (AT)	England	Children like to deal more with a plain and featureless robot over human-robot.
[19] /2007	Keepon robot	Qualitative and quantitative analysis.	Japan	The robot Keepon improves social skills and feel.
[20] /2008	Human or a robot arm model	Assistive Technology (AT)	Italy	The robot helps children to move and act faster.
[21] /2008	AIBO Dog robot (Kasha).	Comparison Study (CA)	USA	AIBO robot enhances children's spoken abilities and engagement.
[22] /2008	Mobile robot (Tito)	Experimental Study based mobile robot and human being.	Canada	Tito enhances children's skills like visual contact and physical proximity more than a human tutor.
[23] / 2009	Therapeutic-assisted robot	Mixture Gaussian-based cluster method.	Japan.	Results show that the robot helps to build engagement between children and robots as mediators.
[24] / 2009	Social Assistive Robotics	Experimental Study of ASD therapy-based robot systems.	Australia	The robot socially assistive in a therapeutic setting for children with ASD.
[25] / 2009	Mobile robot	Conversation Analysis (CA)	England	The robot analyses the boys talking and extract the monotonous speech.
[26] / 2009	Zoomorphic robot	Experimental Study based mechanical dog robot.	USA	The results show that the robot enhances social skills.
[27] / 2009	Modular robotic tiles	Experimental Study based mechanical tiles and Neural system modules.	Spain	The results showed improved social interaction effects in individuals mimicking autistic children with 88% exactness.
[28] / 2010	LEGO robot	Experimental Study based robot with Four scenarios.	England.	Enhance the association with robots and improve the social communication of youths with both autism and mental impairment.
[29] /2010	LEGO robot	Experimental Study of mechanical technology class based robot.	USA	The results show an increase in social interactions.

[30] /2011	Social Assistive Robot	Experimental Study based robot.	Spain	The robot measures the positive, and negative feedback depends on the behavior of the participant. The robot increases the social behavior of children.
[31] / 2012	NAO robot	Experimental Study based NAO robots.	Malaysia	They are proposing guidelines, rules, and procedures to serve as therapy for children with autism.
[32] /2012	Mobile robot	Experimental Study based mobile robot.	France	Used a robot-child as a mediator to express positive emotion in the therapist session.
[33] /2014	penguin PABI robot	Experimental Study based penguin PABI robot.	USA	The children are engaged and communicated more with the humanoid robot.
[34] / 2015	KASPAR humanoid-robot	Experimental Study based KASPAR robot.	USA	The robot helps children with autism to increase body awareness, self-sense, and collaborative play.
[35] / 2016	KASPAR robot	Experimental Study based MILO robot.	USA	The Robot helped children to recognize and convey their feelings and apply calming abilities and meaningful discussion.
[36] /2016	Pepper Robot	Experimental Study based Pepper robot.	USA	The robot helped autistic children to enhance the concept of emotions and learning.
[37] /2017	MILO robot	Experimental Study based MILO robot.	USA	The results show that autistic children are more engaged with the Milo robot than with a physician therapist.
[38] /2017	NAO, KASPAR, Robota, Probo	Review Study based of using different robots like NAO, KASPAR, Robota, Probo.	USA	The results show that the robots enhance the social interactions and communication skills of ASD children.

Figure 2. The propose interactive teaching framework